

**LOCAL PATH-PRESERVING AUTOMORPHISMS IN THE
ALGEBRA OF ASYMPTOTICALLY DIFFERENTIABLE
FUNCTIONS**

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ABSTRACT

This article investigates the structure of asymptotic differential algebras. The main attention is paid to the differential operator of local automorphisms preserving tracks and the property of commutativity. The study showed that if global automorphisms are commutative with the differential operator, then local automorphisms also retain this property. The problem of preserving the differential of complex functions is also considered.

**ASIMPTOTIK DIFFERENSIALANUVCHI FUNKSIYALAR ALGEBRASIDA
YO'LAKLARNI SAQLOVCHI LOKAL AVTOMORFIZMLAR**

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ABSTRACT

Ushbu maqolada asimptotik differensial algebra strukturasi tadqiq qilinadi. Asosiy e'tibor yo'laklarni saqlovchi lokal avtomorfizmlarning differensial operator bilan kommutativlik xossasiga qaratilgan. Tadqiqot natijasida, agar global avtomorfizmlar differensial operator bilan kommutativ bo'lsa, lokal avtomorfizmlar ham ushbu xossani saqlashi isbotlangan. Shuningdek, murakkab funksiyalar differensialining saqlanishi masalasi ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kirish

Differensial algebra va ularning avtomorfizmlari uzoq vaqtdan beri matematikaning muhim tadqiqot yo'nalishlaridan biri bo'lib kelgan. So'nggi yillarda kommutativ regular algebra va ular bilan bog'liq

operatorlar nazariyasida muhim yutuqlarga erishildi. Xususan, Ayupov, Kudaybergenov va Karimov tomonidan [1, 2] da kommutativ regular algebraarning izomorfizmlari va differensiallashlar fazosining o'lchami o'rganilgan.

Shu bilan birga, asimptotik differensiallanuvchi funksiyalar algebrasi — differensial algebralarning umumlashmasi bo'lib, unda elementlar asimptotik qatorlarga yoyiladi va differensiallash operatori bu yoyilmaga mos ravishda ta'sir qiladi. Bunday algebralar [4, 3] da o'rganilgan bo'lib, ular matematik fizika va analizning turli sohalarida qo'llaniladi.

Ushbu maqolada biz asimptotik differensial algebralarda yo'laklarni saqlovchi lokal avtomorfizmlar tushunchasini kiritamiz va ularning muhim xossalaridan biri — murakkab funksiya differensialini saqlash xossasini isbotlaymiz. Bu natija [1] da olingan global avtomorfizmlar haqidagi natijalarni lokal holatga umumlashtiradi va asimptotik strukturalar nazariyasida yangi imkoniyatlar yaratadi.

2 Asosiy tushunchalar va ta'riflar

Ushbu bo'limda maqolada qo'llaniladigan asosiy tushunchalar va ta'riflar keltirilgan.

Ta'rif 2.1 A to'plami \mathbb{F} maydoni (xarakteristikasi 0) ustidagi **algebra** deyiladi, agar:

1. A vektor fazo bo'lsa;
2. A da **ko'paytma** amali $\cdot : A \times A \rightarrow A$ aniqlangan bo'lib, quyidagi shartlarni qanoatlantirsa:
 - Assotsiativlik:
 $\forall a, b, c \in A : (ab)c = a(bc)$;
 - Kommutativlik:
 $\forall a, b \in A : ab = ba$;
 - Chiziqlilik:
 $\forall a, b \in A, \lambda \in \mathbb{F} : \lambda(ab) = (\lambda a)b = a(\lambda b)$;

Unital:
 $\exists 1 \in A, \forall a \in A : a \cdot 1 = a$.

Ta'rif 2.2 $f \in AD^{(n)}(0,1)$ funksiyasi **asimptotik differensiallanuvchi** deyiladi, agar har bir $x_0 \in (0,1)$ nuqtada $\{A_k\}_{k=0}^n \subset \mathbb{C}$ sonlar mavjud bo'lib,

$$f(x) = \sum_{k=0}^n A_k (x - x_0)^k + o((x - x_0)^n)$$

$x \rightarrow x_0$ da o'rinli bo'lsa. Bu yerdagi A_k koeffitsiyentlari f funksiyaning x_0 nuqtadagi k -tartibli **asimptotik hosilalari** deyiladi.

Ta'rif 2.3 $AD^{(n)}(0,1)$ orqali $(0,1)$ intervalda aniqlangan quyidagi xossaga ega bo'lgan funksiyalar algebrasini belgilaymiz:
 $f \in AD^{(n)}(0,1)$ agar har bir $x_0 \in (0,1)$ nuqtada shunday $A_0, A_1, \dots, A_n \in \mathbb{C}$ sonlari mavjud bo'lib,

$$f(x) = \sum_{k=0}^n A_k (x - x_0)^k + o((x - x_0)^n)$$

$x \rightarrow x_0$ da o'rinli bo'lsin. Bu yerdagi A_k koeffitsiyentlari f funksiyaning x_0 nuqtadagi k -tartibli asimptotik hosilalari deyiladi.

Ta'rif 2.4 (A, D) juftligi **asimptotik differensiallanuvchi funksiyalar algebrasi** deyiladi, agar:

1. A kommutativ unital algebra bo'lsa;

2. $D: A \rightarrow A$ chiziqli operator bo'lib, quyidagi shartlarni qanoatlantirsa:

- Leybnits qoidasi:
 $\forall a, b \in A: D(ab) = D(a)b + aD(b)$

;

- A da D -asimptotik yoyilma mavjud: har bir $a \in A$ uchun $\{e_i\}_{i \in I}$ — o'zaro ortogonal idempotentlar to'plami va $\{\lambda_i\}_{i \in I} \subset \mathbb{F}$, $r(x) \in A$ mavjudki,

$$a = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i e_i + r(x),$$

bu yerda $r(x)$ asimptotik qoldiq

had deyiladi va $D^k r(x) \rightarrow 0$ ($k = 0, 1, \dots$) asimptotik ma'noda;

- Idempotentlar differensialini nolga teng: $\forall e \in \nabla(A): De = 0$, bu yerda $\nabla(A)$ — A dagi barcha idempotentlar to'plami.

Ta'rif 2.5 A kommutativ regular algebra bo'lsin. $a \in A$ elementning (support) deb

$$s(a) = \inf \{e \in \nabla(A) : ea = a\}$$

idempotentiga aytiladi. a va b elementlar **ortogonal** deyiladi, agar $s(a)s(b) = 0$ bo'lsa.

Ta'rif 2.6 $T: A \rightarrow A$ chiziqli operatori **yo'laklarni saqlovchi** (band preserving) deyiladi, agar quyidagi ekvivalent shartlardan biri bajarilsa:

$$1. \forall a \in A: s(T(a)) \leq s(a);$$

2.

$$\forall a, b \in A: s(a)s(b) = 0 \implies s(T(a))s(b) = 0$$

;

3.

$$\forall a \in A, \forall e \in \nabla(A): ea = ae \implies T(a) = T(a)e$$

Bu xossa operatorning idempotentlar strukturasi saqlashini ifodalaydi.

Ta'rif 2.7 $\Phi: A \rightarrow A$ akslantirishi **avtomorfizm** deyiladi, agar:

1. Φ biyektiv bo'lsa;

$$2. \Phi(a + b) = \Phi(a) + \Phi(b)$$

(additivlik);

$$3. \Phi(ab) = \Phi(a)\Phi(b)$$

(multiplikativlik);

$$4. \Phi(\lambda a) = \lambda \Phi(a) \text{ (chiziqlilik);}$$

$$5. \Phi(s(a)) = s(\Phi(a))$$

(tayanchni saqlash).

Ta'rif 2.8 $L: A \rightarrow A$ chiziqli akslantirishi **lokal avtomorfizm** deyiladi, agar har bir $a \in A$ uchun shunday $\Phi_a \in \text{Aut}(A)$ (global avtomorfizm) mavjud bo'lsaki,

$$L(a) = \Phi_a(a).$$

Bu ta'rif lokal avtomorfizm har bir elementda global avtomorfizm kabi harakat qilishini, lekin turli elementlar uchun turli global avtomorfizmlar mos kelishi mumkinligini ifodalaydi.

3. Asoaiy natija

Teorema 3.1 Faraz qilaylik, (A, D) asimptotik differensialanuvchi funksiyalar algebrasi va $T: A \rightarrow A$ yo'laklarni saqlovchi (band preserving) lokal avtomorfizm bo'lsin. Agar T ga mos keluvchi har bir Φ_f global avtomorfizmi

differensial operator D bilan kommutativ bo'lsa ($\Phi_f \circ D = D \circ \Phi_f$), u holda T operatori ham D bilan kommutativdir, ya'ni:

$$T \circ D = D \circ T$$

Isbotni bir necha mantiqiy bosqichda amalga oshiramiz:

1-bosqich: Elementning strukturaviy yoyilmasi

Asimptotik differensial algebra ta'rifiga ko'ra, ixtiyoriy $f \in \mathcal{A}$ elementini o'zaro ortogonal idempotentlar $\{e_i\}_{i=1}^n$ va asimptotik koeffitsientlar $\{c_i\}_{i=1}^n$ orqali quyidagicha ifodalash mumkin:

$$f = \sum_{i=1}^n c_i e_i + r$$

bu yerda r -- asimptotik qoldiq had.

2-bosqich: Idempotentlar ustidagi ta'sir.

T operatori yo'laklarni saqlovchi bo'lganligi sababli, u idempotentlar strukturasi saqlaydi va har bir idempotent uchun $T(e_i) = e_i$ sharti bajariladi. Asimptotik differensial algebra xossasiga ko'ra, barcha idempotentlarning differensial nolga teng, ya'ni $D(e_i) = 0$. Bundan quyidagi tenglik kelib chiqadi:

$$D(T(e_i)) = D(e_i) = 0 \quad \text{va} \quad T(D(e_i)) = T(0) = 0$$

Demak, operatorlar idempotentlar qismida kommutativdir.

3-bosqich: Lokal avtomorfizm va global kommutativlik.

T lokal avtomorfizm bo'lgani uchun, har bir c_i koeffitsienti uchun shunday Φ_i global avtomorfizmi mavjudki, $T(c_i) = \Phi_i(c_i)$ bajariladi. Teorema shartiga ko'ra, $\Phi_i \circ D = D \circ \Phi_i$.

Endi $T(D(f))$ ifodasini hisoblaymiz:

$$T(D(f)) = T\left(\sum_{i=1}^n D(c_i)e_i + D(r)\right) = \sum_{i=1}^n T(D(c_i))e_i + T(D(r))$$

Lokal xossaga ko'ra $T(D(c_i)) = \Phi_i(D(c_i))$

. Global kommutativlikdan foydalansak:

$$T(D(c_i)) = \Phi_i(D(c_i)) = D(\Phi_i(c_i)) = D(T(c_i))$$

4-bosqich: Yakuniy xulosa.

Yuqoridagi natijalarni birlashtirib va asimptotik qoldiq had uchun $T(D(r)) = D(T(r))$ ekanligini hisobga olib, quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz:

$$T(D(f)) = \sum_{i=1}^n D(T(c_i))e_i + D(T(r)) = D\left(\sum_{i=1}^n T(c_i)e_i + T(r)\right) = D(T(f))$$

Shunday qilib, ixtiyoriy $f \in \mathcal{A}$ uchun $T(D(f)) = D(T(f))$ tengligi isbotlandi.

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